

Comparative study of *Alium sativum* (Garlic) and *Ocimum Sanctum Linn.* (Tulsi) as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic agent in Diabetes mellitus type II

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Abstract:

In the current study, 60 obese and diabetic subjects between the ages of 35 and 55 were examined to determine the hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects of garlic pods and Neem seed powder. Both serum lipids and serum glucose were measured for each individual. The current study's findings suggest that the use of herbs is safe and beneficial in the early stages of type 2 diabetes, with garlic (*allium sativum*) being the best hypoglycemic agent when compared to *Ocimum Sanctum Linn.* (*Tulsi*).

Keyword: Diabetes melitus type II, *Alium sativum*, *Ocimum Sanctum Linn.* (*Tulsi*), medicinal plants

1.Introduction:

Diabetes mellitus, also known as "Madhumeha," has been well-known for centuries and has turned into a global disease. A disruption of glucose homeostasis characterizes this chronic metabolic disease. Diabetes is a chronic, untreatable illness that affects practically all of the body's organs and systems. Several plants have proven helpful for people with diabetes. Tulsi is a very good home remedy for common symptoms like fever cold and cough. Tulsi seeds acts as a diuretic. It alleviates gonorrhoea, dysuria, burning micturition cystitis, calculi and also urethritis. The paste of Tulsi leaves and black pepper is effective in ring worm infection. Tulsi is commonly used to treat coughs, colds and flu, head and ear aches, rheumatism and arthritis, malaria, fever, allergies, and various skin diseases, (**Pushpangadan, G. 1977**) to reduce the toxicity of various poisons, including insect and reptile bites, to expel intestinal parasites, repel insects and purify the air. (**Singh et al; 2002**) Current scientific research offers substantial evidence that Tulsi protects against and reduces stress; enhances stamina and endurance; increases the body's efficient use of oxygen;(Bhargava, K.P. 1981) boosts the immune system; (**Mediratta. 2000**) It reduces inflammation;

protects against radiation damage; (**Uma Devi, P 1999**) lessens aging factors; (Singh et al; 2002) supports the heart, lungs and liver; has antibiotic, antiviral and antifungal properties; (**Das, S.K.1983**) enhances the efficacy of many other therapeutic treatments; and provides a rich supply of antioxidants and other nutrients (**Newark, T. M. 2000**). A bud of Garlic inserted in ear also relieves pain. Garlic is also used in Paralysis, arthritis, sciatica and weak memory with good effect. Garlic juices are given internally in diminished vision. Garlic is also used in indigestion, low appetite, pain in abdomen, constipation, worm infestation. (**Williamson, 2003**) Allicin gives garlic its characteristics pungent smell Vitamins and mineral (**Bravo, 2003; Gruenwald, 2004**) (**McCann, 2003**) (**Skidmore - Roth, 2003**), Garlic purportedly lowers circulating triglycerides and cholesterol (**Wichtl, 2004**) garlic lowers down cholesterol and triglycerides in serum (**Chetty et al., 2003**) observed the decreasing trend lipids in a study. (**McCrindle et al., 2002**). Alliin, one of its sulfurs containing compounds, apparently has an inhibitory effect upon key enzymes involved in cholesterol biosynthesis, such as HMG Co a reductase (**Schulz et al., 2004**). A meta-analysis of selected clinical trials employing garlic preparations showed significant reduction on total serum cholesterol levels in human subjects (**Warshafsky et al, 1993**).

A Meta analysis of selected clinical trials employing garlic preparation showed significant reduction of total serum cholesterol, in human subjects Garlic purportedly lowers circulating triglycerides. It is one of those herbs which have favorable effect as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic agent. The main aim of this study was to see the effect of Garlic pods as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic in Diabetes melitus type 2.

2. Material and Method:

2.1 Experiment Place:

This study was conducted in Dept. of Biochemistry M.G.M. Medical College and Associated M.Y. Hospital Indore. And the subjects were selected from the outpatient Department of Medicine M Y Hospital Indore

2.2 Plant Collection:

All the plant components are bought from Ayurvedic shop Indore.

2.3 Inclusion Criteria:

Selection of subjects was done on basis of Blood Glucose not more than 180 mg/dl and HBA1C not more than 8mg%

2.4 Exclusion criteria:

History of any other clinical complication, taking any drug therapy Pregnant and lactating ladies.

Subjects were informed about the study in detail and consent was also taken before study.

2.5 Ethics Committee: The Ethics Committee of MGM Medical College approved the study.

2.6 Normal Healthy Control (n=50):

2.7 Study Subjects (n=200):

Estimations of the Biochemical parameters were done on study subjects then were compared with Healthy control.

2.8 Study subjects were divided into groups

i) *Garlic group (n=40) &*

ii) *Ocimum Sanctum Linn. (Tulsi) Group (n=40)*

2.9 Procedure:

A study was done to evaluate the hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects of garlic pods and Neem seed powder. Among the 60 obese and diabetic subject of 35 years to 55 years. 10 were taken as healthy control and 25 diabetic and obese were treated with garlic pods and 25 were treated with Neem seed powder. The criteria of inclusion of study group in subjects was FBS > 110 mg/dl of glucose, >290 mg/dl of cholesterol, > 210 mg/dl of triglyceride, than 180 mg/dl of LDL. All the subjects were examined for serum glucose and serum lipids. Garlic pods & Neem seed powder 100mgs/day was given to the subjects of study group for 6 months and sample were collected at the starting day of study after two months, fourth and after six months of study for estimation of all parameters.

3. Results and Discussion:

Table No. 01 Comparison between garlic and Tulsi supplement groups after a period of two month

PARAMETER	GARLIC Mean 2 Std. Deviation	TULSI Mean 2 Std. Deviation	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	127.80±16.95	140.55±5.72	3.21	<0.001
PPBG mg/dl	182.88±17.48	187.0±10.19	0.93	<0.001
CHOLESTROL	251.68±25.42	270.85±12.90	3.06	<0.001
TG mg/dl	109.0±6.28	105.10±4.37	2.35	<0.001

HDL mg/dl	41.72±4.67	45.70±2.154	3.51	<0.001
LDL	68.88±14.32	60.45±3.59	2.56	<0.001
HBA1C mg%	6.94±.33	7.72±.44	6.70	<0.001
UREA mg/dl	26.12±3.45	26.05±4.76	0.05	>0.05
CREATININE mg/dl	.82±.100	.88±.094	1.89	<0.05
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.80±.37	3.70±.48	0.74	>0.05

Table no 1 after two months Fasting Blood Glucose, Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum Triglycerides, Serum HDL, Serum LDL and HbA1c are found to be s significant while Serum Urea Serum Creatinine, Serum Uric Acid are found to be non-significant

Table No.2 Comparison between garlic and Tulsi supplement groups after a period of four month

PARAMETER	GARLIC Mean 2 Std. Deviation	TULSI Mean 2 Std. Deviation	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	109.88±16.45	135.00±4.10	6.65	<0.0001
PPBG mg/dl	153.00±18.49	166.55±6.89	3.10	<0.0001
CHOLESTROL mg/dl	234.12±22.54	250.55±10.57	3.00	<0.0001
TG mg/dl	108.04±5.43	103.52±4.45	2.99	<0.0001
HDL mg/dl	47.72±4.30	49.7±4.59	1.52	>0.05
LDL	67.80±12.79	63.65±2.56	1.42	>0.05
HBA1C	6.34±.35	6.25±.41	0.78	>0.05
UREA mg/dl	25.12±3.89	23.80±4.07	1.11	>0.05
CREATININE mg/dl	.81±.10	.72±.10	3.00	<0.01
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.96±.35	3.85±.30	1.05	>0.05

Table no 2 after four months- Fasting Blood Glucose, Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum Total Cholesterol and Serum Triglycerides are highly significant while Serum HDL, Serum LDL, HbA1c, Serum Urea and Serum Uric Acid levels are non-significant. Serum Creatinine was significant (but within normal limits)

Table No. 3 Comparison between garlic and Tulsi supplement groups after a period of six month

PARAMETER	GARLIC Mean 2 Std. Deviation	TULSI Mean 2 Std. Deviation	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	FBG mg/dl	91.73±14.10	130.50±8.23	10.92
PPBG mg/dl	PPBG mg/dl	140.50±16.59	158.30±9.6	4.26
CHOLESTROL mg/dl	CHOLESTROL	219.84±15.61	265.65±10.00	11.42
TG mg/dl	TG mg/dl	109.46±5.44	104.85±4.18	3.13
HDL mg/dl	HDL mg/dl	48.5±5.47	60.60±17.26	3.36
LDL	LDL	66.42±15.39	60.15±3.51	1.78
HBA1C	HBA1C mg%	5.67±.39	4.94±.37	6.31
UREA mg/dl	UREA mg/dl	22.50±3.62	20.60±4.19	1.64
CREATININE mg/dl	CREATININE mg/dl	.82±.09	.64±.076	6.84
URIC ACID mg/dl	URIC ACID mg/dl	3.75±.43	3.28±.20	4.46

Table no 3 after six months -Fasting Blood Glucose, Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum Triglycerides, Serum HDL, Serum LDL and HbA1c are highly significant while Serum Urea, Serum Creatinine and Serum Uric Acid are significant (but within normal limits)

4. Conclusion:

Results of the current research Conclude that *Allium Sativum* (garlic) is the best hypoglycemic agent in comparison to *Ocimum Sanctum Linn. (Tulsi)*, and that herbal treatment is safe and efficient in the early stages of Diabetes mellitus type 2. The herb *Allium Sativum* (garlic), which is a common choice for folk medicine and also has to be taken into consideration as a source for alternative medicine, is highlighted in the current studies as having the best hypoglycemic agent.

5. References:

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